

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT AND MODERN VIEW OF CAPITAL MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN

Tashkent Institute of Finance

Banking accounting, analysis and audit science

Akbar Abdurazakov Abdurakhmon oqli

Annotation: The article devoted to open background progress of capital markets in Uzbekistan and view of nowadays. Moreover, in the article role of credit market in the finance system and its close connection with capital market were highlighted.

Key words: *household budgetary, economic reform, loan portfolio, venture obligation, commercial banks, secondary market trading, treasury bills.*

Uzbekistan has delighted in generally solid financial development in later a long time since of a favorable send out environment and judicious monetary and financial approaches. Current account adjust has been positive for the final 9 a long time but for 2001 and as a result, the outside trade saves are evaluated to have risen to roughly 10 billion dollars. But, from the moment half of 2008, the economy begun abating as the worldwide financial downturn is affecting the economy. The household budgetary division was not specifically influenced due to the separated and immature nature of the money related framework. The banking sector and capital market in Uzbekistan is not yet well developed. The government has taken a gradual approach in economic reform. Similarly, reforms in the banking sector and capital market are slowly undertaken. The deposit base and penetration (ratio of loans and assets to GDP) are one of the lowest in CIS countries. As indicated in Figure 1, credit to economy/GDP and broad money /GDP are quite low. Credit to economy was about 38% of GDP in 2001, however,

it declined to around 14% in 2007, which was low compared to other CIS countries. The state-owned banks are predominant in the banking system[1]. Over half of the assets, capital, and loan portfolio in the Uzbek banking are possessed by state banks. The banking system is concentrated in Uzbekistan since the five largest banks own 70% of assets. Government guaranteed loans are still significant, albeit they are declining every year.

Uzbekistan had to begin from the scratch in building the capital markets, since markets for government obligation, venture obligation, and values were truant when the nation got to be free in 1991. The capital showcase in Uzbekistan is at the beginning arrange and still exceptionally little. In 2006, capitalization of equity market was only 1.6 billion dollars, equivalent to 10.2% of GDP. In Central Asia, the Kazak capital market is the most developed, where capitalization of equity market was 56.6 billion dollars, equivalent to 70.4% of GDP in 2006 (Table 2 & 3). Equity issues have begun during 1990s in the process of mass privatization and de-monopolization. The majority of equity issues were carried out by non-listed companies, while the equity issues of listed companies were not so significant. There were 1925 joint stock companies registered in Uzbekistan in 2007, of which 75 % are state-owned. The nominal value of the shares of all joint stock companies amount to \$2.5 billion equivalent. At the end of 2007, only 10 companies were listed on the Republic Stock Exchange Tashkent (RSET). However, the number has increased to 18 as of end of June 2008, albeit very small. The majority of the listed companies are commercial banks, most of which are state owned or controlled. In 2007, 163 shares amounting to approximately \$380 million equivalent were issued, of which \$301 million (1.4% of GDP) equivalent were not related to privatization. The largest issuer was the oil and gas company Uzneftegazkazibchikarish (\$77 million equivalent), followed by Uzpromstroybank (\$56 million), Pakhtabank (\$50 million), Gallabank (\$30 million), Mikrokreditbank (\$17 million), and Chirchikskiy Transformator Plant

(\$14 million). Altogether, 18 banks issued shares which amounted to \$196 million equivalent in 2007. By sector, banks were the most active equity issuers. This is because capital requirements for banks have been increased and banks were required to sell at least 25% of issues through the stock exchange. In Uzbekistan, only a small amount of shares are issued through the stock exchange; only \$38 million equivalent was raised at the exchange in 2007. It is estimated that the amount of capital raised in 2007 was about 1 % of GDP. Secondary market is characterized by thin turnover. In 2007, less than 9,000 transactions took place at the stock exchange, namely, around 40 on average per trading day. An additional 1,200 transactions occurred at the formal OTC market. In terms of amount secondary market trading was equivalent to mere \$71 million equivalent, of which the stock exchange accounted for 86% and the rest was by the OTC market. Foreign investors are allowed to invest in the stock exchange and they are mainly from EU, Korea, German, US, and Russia. Approximate share of foreign investor turnover is 15%. RSET began to calculate a share index called "Tasix" from 2000. As volumes of trades and share prices remain volatile, the index fluctuation has been extremely high. The index was 107 on May 7 in 2007, declined to 20 on September 7 in 2007, rose to 513 on September 8 in 2008, fell to 97 on December 8 in 2008, and again rose to 663 on January 9 in 2009, indicating volatile and speculative market[2].

Bond market is at an early stage of development. Bond market is comprised of government, central bank bills and corporate bonds. Prior to 1996, there were no debt instruments. In March 1996, 3 month treasury bills were issued for the first time, and 6 month treasury bills were issued in the following year. Central Bank also issued bills. The major aim of the government in issuing T-bills was to finance budget deficits using non-inflationary source. The Central Bank issued bills in an attempt to conduct open market operations to influence market liquidity and market interest rates. In addition, the government started to issue 9 month and

12 month treasury bills during 1998-1999. The number of issues and the volume of shorter treasury bills have been on the decrease since the introduction of longer maturity bills and more than half of treasury bills are now accounted for by maturity in excess of 12 months. However, access to treasury bills was restricted to legal entities and residents of Uzbekistan. According to the Central Bank, the market in treasury bills was very shallow with only 19% of the outstanding stock held by the non-bank public in January 2005. This is due primarily to (1) low yields compared to inflation and the high return on holding foreign currency notes; (2) the absence of permission for banks to sell the bonds to the public outside the auction; and (3) the non-existence of repurchase agreement operations between banks and the public based on the T-bills in banks' portfolios. Consequently, the development of government securities is limited and they do not provide benchmarks due to illiquid secondary market. Corporate bond market did not exist until 1999, when only a small amount of corporate bond was issued for the first time. During 2000-2001, the bond was issued, but in small amounts. Corporate bond market was somewhat invigorated from 2002, as regulatory changes removed restrictions on the size of corporate bond issues[3]. However, the corporate bond market is hampered due to poor market infrastructure, limited institutional investors and lack of creditworthy private companies. In recognition of the importance to develop an orderly, fair and efficient capital market for resource mobilization, intermediation and investment opportunity, the government obtained a Technical Assistance¹ from the Asian Development Bank in 2003.

As capital market is not yet developed, banks play a predominant role in corporate finance in Uzbekistan. Credit market is the main source for corporate finance followed by equity market, and bond market is still insignificant in corporate finance. In Central Asia, Kazakhstan is the most developed country in equity and bond market. Banking sector assets were equivalent to 33% of GDP in Uzbekistan in 2007. This figure is substantially low compared to 92% of GDP in

Kazakhstan, but slightly higher than that in the Kyrgyz Republic. The banking sector is highly concentrated and segmented. As of the end of 2007 there were 28 banks including 5 banks with foreign participation (Table 4). The Uzbek banking sector is concentrated; large state-owned financial institutions with three fully state-owned banks accounting for 56% of total assets and 60% of total capital of the entire banking system. The National Bank of Uzbekistan, a state-owned bank, is the largest commercial banking institution in Uzbekistan, and state banks are virtually the agents of the government in implementing the government development strategy. While there are private banks and banks with foreign participation they are still small niche players. The non-performing loans ranged between 3.0 and 10.9 % during 2000-2006. However, they are presumably higher because, in principle, banks do not have to make provisions against government guaranteed loans[4]. The banks are closely monitored by the government, which imposes non-core functions including tax withholding and financial oversight of firms on the banks. Therefore, the confidence in the banking sector is very low in Uzbekistan, resulting in low deposit rates and low intermediation. International financial institutions are of the view that the banking sector needs to be reformed so as to become one of the key drivers of the economy. The goal of the reforms is to attain a reliable banking system, which can provide business enterprises and sectors of economy with sufficient financial resources. In order to materialize this, the banking sector is required to gain confidence and trust as well as reducing the intervention by the state.

To sum up, it should be noted that the development of commercial banking in Uzbekistan has been affected by direct government intervention in foreign exchange and financial markets. Initially, the rule limiting enterprises to hold accounts with only one bank was introduced, which seriously undermined competition among banks. Moreover, enterprise deposits were allowed to be withdrawn only for the payment of wages and travel expenses in accordance with

quarterly cash plans. Both rules were abolished at a later stage (in 1998 and 2002, respectively), which should improve competition among banks and increase the trustworthiness of the banking sector. However, market-based finance remains largely underdeveloped and banks play only a limited role in the intermediation of domestic savings.

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